

JUSTICE IN SENTENCING: LEGAL CRITERIA FOR PROPORTIONALITY AND INDIVIDUALIZATION

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Abstract: This article analyzes the implementation of the principle of justice in the sentencing process within the field of criminal law. The main focus is on the principles of proportionality and individualization of punishment. The article examines the legal criteria for sentencing, their interrelation, and their application in international and national legal practice, as well as the effectiveness and challenges of these principles in judicial activities. The study reveals the theoretical and practical significance of proportionality and individualization in ensuring fairness in punishment and puts forward proposals for improving their legal mechanisms.

Keywords: Sentencing, principle of justice, proportionality of punishment, individualization, legal criteria, criminal law, proportionality, judicial law, individualization of punishment

The principle of justice in criminal law is significant not only as a theoretical category but also as a practical criterion that establishes criminal liability, determines the type and measure of punishment, and ensures the legality and validity of court decisions. Specifically, requirements such as the proportionality of punishment, an individual approach to the person, and equality before the law acquire their legal substance through the principle of justice. Therefore, it is of critical importance to analyze the mechanisms through which this principle manifests in criminal law and criminal procedure relations.

"Justice as the essence of law and morality can only be grasped through continuous measurement and comparison." [1] Since justice is a relative concept, it implies the comparison and measurement of behavior (actions) and their evaluation, deeds, and punishments.

In the history of moral doctrines, justice was often viewed as a purely legal category. This is also confirmed by linguistic data. For example, in Latin, "justice" and "justitia" (justitia) are synonyms, while in French, the concept of "legitime" (law) means justice and conformity to law.

Applied to the nature of legal liability, "justice is a morally valid criterion for measuring the actions of subjects, according to which everyone is punished according to their deeds" [2].

At the same time, "justice in liability is reflected in the equality of all citizens before the sanction of the law, the correct determination of the type of liability and the degree of public danger of the offense (crime or other act), the correct definition of the measure of liability in the law, and its correct application by law enforcement agencies" [3].

In the process of studying the operation of justice, V. E. Davidovich identified three specific directions for performing its two functions: justice as an assessment and criterion of goals, justice as an assessment and criterion of means, and justice as an assessment and criterion of results [4].

At the same time, it should be assumed that "an assessment of actions in accordance with the criterion of justice is appropriate only if it is clear that at least two subjects (individuals,

social groups, classes, states) have interacted" [5]. Thus, it can be concluded that justice is determined by two actions: measurement and evaluation.

Below, we will use this same rule to determine the degree of justice of the types and amounts of criminal penalties established in the Criminal Code by comparing the sanctions of several articles of the Criminal Code. In particular, the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan contains 34 provisions providing for liability for causing moderate or severe bodily harm through negligence, and the types and amounts of punishment provided for in the sanctions of these articles differ sharply from each other. In certain articles (Art. 1863 of the Criminal Code). 1 of the Criminal Code), and in some cases (Art. 116 of the Criminal Code). 2) provides for up to four types of punishment. At the same time, the amounts and terms of punishment differ from each other.

Justice as a category is of particular importance for jurisprudence, various legal institutions, and certain legal norms.

In 1994, a new category of justice was introduced into the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the country's criminal legislation, and the application of criminal law norms for sentencing was established as a principle that the court must adhere to.

In Article 2 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the RSFSR of 1960, among the tasks of criminal proceedings was also proclaimed "ensuring the correct application of the law so that a just punishment may be imposed on every person who has committed a crime," i.e., the principle of justice was established indirectly, in its abstract form[6]. Article 37 of the Criminal Code of the Uzbek SSR of 1959 also states that "when sentencing, the court, guided by socialist legal consciousness, takes into account the nature and degree of public danger of the committed crime, the personality of the perpetrator, and the mitigating and aggravating circumstances of the case." As we can see, during the Soviet era, "legal consciousness" was at the forefront of criminal law and also determined the fairness of the imposed punishment.

Even today, the criterion of justice is of great importance not only for the criminal law of the Republic of Uzbekistan but also for criminal proceedings.

Article 2 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to Part 1, the tasks of criminal procedural legislation are to quickly and fully reveal crimes, expose the guilty, and ensure the correct application of the law so that every person who has committed a crime is given a fair punishment, and no innocent person is prosecuted or convicted[8].

Part one of Article 455 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes the criterion of justice alongside the criteria of legality and validity, which the sentence must satisfy. Part four states that a sentence or other measure of influence against a guilty person is recognized as fair if it is assigned taking into account the degree of public danger of the crime committed and their personality, and if an innocent person is acquitted and rehabilitated [9]. The unfairness of the punishment serves as grounds for the reversal or modification of the sentence (Art. 485 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan). 1-q. P. 5). A punishment is considered unjust if it does not correspond to the gravity of the crime or the personality of the convicted person, or if the punishment was imposed without exceeding the limits provided for by the relevant article of the Special Part of the Criminal Code, but is excessively lenient or excessively severe by type or standard (Article 490 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, titled "Injustice of Punishment") [10].

In accordance with part one of Article 60 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Courts," a person elected or appointed to a judicial position for the first time shall assume their duties after taking the following oath: "I solemnly swear to perform my duties honestly and conscientiously, to administer justice only in accordance with the law, and to be impartial, impartial, and fair as my judicial duty and conscience dictate."

As we can see, in criminal proceedings, the criterion of justice is of great importance for the legislator, as it means that the exposure of the guilty and the correct application of laws, punishment or other measures of influence are proportional to the degree of social danger of the committed crime and the personality of the perpetrator.

Previously, criminologists sometimes referred to the principle of justice as the proportionality of punishment to the degree of social danger of the crime[12]. The principle of individualization of punishment is also sometimes mentioned.

"Justice encompasses all other principles, unites them, and manifests itself in practice through them"[13]. Indeed, a deeper study of this term reveals that all the principles of legality, equality of citizens before the law, democracy, humanism, justice, responsibility for guilt, and the inevitability of responsibility enshrined in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan contain elements of criminal justice.

In criminal law, the principle of justice should be formulated more broadly—directly addressed to both the law enforcer and the legislator. Therefore, the principle of justice should be formulated in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan in such a way that the legislator must strictly adhere to it when establishing sanctions. To this end, it is proposed to amend part one of Article 8 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, generally stating the specified norm in the following wording:

Article 8. Principle of fairness

A person shall be held liable for a socially dangerous act for which their guilt has been proven in accordance with the procedure established by law.

Persons who have committed a crime, regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, beliefs, social origin, or social status, have the same rights and obligations and are equal before the law.

The punishment or other legal measure applied to a person guilty of committing a crime must be proportionate, i.e., correspond to the nature and degree of public danger of the committed act, the form of guilt, and the characteristics of the person.

No one may be held liable twice for the same crime.

As noted above, the current criminal-legal principle of justice is based on the international legal principle of the fair application of the law. Article 10 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states: "Everyone shall have the right, in full equality, to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in order to determine his rights and obligations and to determine the merits of the criminal charge against him."[14]

In the declaration, both characteristics of justice are reflected in the definition of the principle of justice given in the law. For "the gravity of the crime" reflects justice from the perspective of the common good and the general prosperity of society. "The degree of public danger of guilt and the individual" is an individual aspect of the nature of justice, which reflects the requirement to take into account various circumstances and the individual aspects and characteristics of each individual. However, "equality and individualization are the two fundamental ideas that define the content of the demand for the justice of punishment"[15].

Individualization of punishment is the assignment of a specific measure of punishment to the perpetrator in full accordance with the nature and degree of public danger of the committed crime, the personality of the perpetrator, and all circumstances of the case, including mitigating and aggravating circumstances.

But the principle of justice and the individualization of punishment are not the same thing. Individualization always concerns the personality of the perpetrator, while in justice, personal and social interests are also taken into account.

Two branches of government—the legislative and judicial branches—participate in determining measures of criminal law impact on persons who have committed crimes. The legislator limits the court's discretion to a clearly defined scope and establishes a sanction, while the court, acting within its established scope, determines the punishment in accordance with the criteria defined by law. In this way, the harmony of the principles of equality, humanism, legality and individualization of punishment will be ensured, and the ground will be created for a fair verdict.

The principle of justice must be observed equally by both the law enforcer and the legislator, while the principle of individualization of punishment, taking into account the principle of justice, is primarily addressed to the court and applies at the time of sentencing. After all, in addition to the nature and degree of public danger of the committed crime, taking into account the personality of the perpetrator, the circumstances of the crime, as well as other mitigating and aggravating circumstances, only the court can fully individualize the punishment. Individualization implies both a deviation from the lower limit of punishment provided for a given crime and the imposition of another, more lenient punishment, as well as the decision to impose a suspended sentence and apply other measures. The main thing is not to forget the rights of the victim, as Article 2 of the Criminal Code. According to Part 1, when applying criminal law, a person's rights, rather than their duties, take precedence.

According to M.Kh. Rustambaev, ..."justice, from the perspective of the Criminal Code, requires that punishment or other legal measures be imposed in accordance with the severity of the criminal act committed, the degree of guilt, and the social danger of the guilty person." Justice, as a principle of criminal law, expresses the proportionality of punishment to the crime committed or the severity of the committed act, the degree of guilt, the social danger of the guilty person, which manifests as an important direction in this case" [16].

According to A.N. Ignatov, "the principle of justice is implemented through the individualization of punishment and responsibility, and this principle means that when sentencing, courts should rely not on feelings or a sense of revenge, but on an objective assessment of the crime committed and the personality of the perpetrator." Justice, on the one hand, must be proportional to the crime committed, and on the other hand, the punishment must correspond to the convict's personality, that is, to all his positive and negative characteristics and qualities, so that the purpose of the punishment can be achieved with the help of this punishment"[17].

L.D. Gauxman, writing about the principle of justice, draws attention to the fact that it is perceived differently by people: "the triumph of justice is not always perceived by the guilty and the victim in the same way, punishment is considered fair only if it is appointed with full consideration of the general grounds for sentencing in the General part of the criminal law, mitigating and aggravating circumstances, etc."[18].

Yu.I. Lyapunov also notes that the principle of justice is one of the important principles of criminal law, "it should be noted that a just punishment requires the courts to fully take into account special principles of criminal law, such as the differentiation of liability and strict individualization of state-legal coercive measures, as well as the correct, law-based qualification of the crime, taking into account the factual circumstances of the case" [19].

V.V. Dyakonov expresses his point of view on this matter as follows: "The principle of justice enshrined in criminal law means that the punishment and other measures of criminal law influence to be applied to the person who committed the crime must be fair, that is, proportional to the degree of severity of the crime, the circumstances of the case and the personality of the perpetrator"[20].

N.F. Kuznesova writes about two aspects of the principle of justice: the justice of the criminal law and the justice of the punishment imposed by the court for the crime.

I.V. Chechelnitskiy emphasized that "the stability and strength of the state system are directly dependent on the extent to which the norms of law established by the state in the process of lawmaking correspond to universal moral norms, especially the most important of which is the norm of justice"[21].

The principle of justice is based on the requirements for the differentiation and individualization of criminal liability. Furthermore, the principle of non-punishment twice for the same crime ("non bis in idem") is one of the principles of both international and constitutional law.

V.V. Koryakovtsev and K.V. Pitulko also expressed an opinion on the principle of justice, noting that "punishment and measures of criminal law influence must correspond to the degree and characteristics of the social danger of the crime and the guilty person" and that "the principle of justice is manifested in practice through the institutions of the general part of the criminal law" [22].

In general, it has been repeatedly emphasized in legal literature that the principle of justice is one of the fundamental guiding principles of criminal law. Therefore, the principle of justice should be reflected in lawmaking and law enforcement practice.

Thus, the principle of justice appears in criminal law as the main legal criterion for the differentiation of criminal liability, the individualization of punishment, and the adoption of a fair decision by the court. It serves as a guiding principle for the legislator in determining sanctions, and for the court in determining punishment in a specific case. From this point of view, it is necessary to further clarify the content of the principle of justice and consistently reflect it in the norms of the law in the improvement of the national criminal legislation

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